

Acute Cardiac Injury Associated With Cocaine Use and Carbon Monoxide Exposure: Two Case Reports

Antonio VILLA^{1*}, Valeria RIVA²

¹Internal Medicine Department, Fatebenefratelli Hospital, ASST Fatebenefratelli and Sacco, Milan, Italy. E-mail: antoniovilla.7956@gmail.com **ORCID:** 0009-0004-1634-6978

²Emergency Department, Pio XII Hospital, ASST Brianza, Desio (MB), Italy. E-mail: valeria.riva@asst-brianza.it **ORCID:** 0009-0000-1577-3936

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

Neurological and cardiovascular complications, including electrocardiographic abnormalities, myocardial ischemia, and malignant arrhythmias, have been reported both after cocaine use and during carbon monoxide intoxication. However, toxicological causes of acute cardiac injury are frequently underestimated in clinical practice, particularly in young patients without traditional cardiovascular risk factors. We present two case reports illustrating the significant clinical relationship between toxic exposure and myocardial damage. The first case involves a young male admitted in coma with tonic–clonic seizures, transient ischemic electrocardiographic changes, and elevated cardiac biomarkers. Initial suspicion focused on cocaine use; however, a detailed reconstruction of the clinical timeline and environmental exposure suggested carbon monoxide intoxication as a more plausible cause, despite delayed carboxyhemoglobin assessment. The second case describes a middle-aged woman presenting with myocardial injury and a potentially malignant ventricular arrhythmia, later attributed to inhaled cocaine use, in the absence of obstructive coronary artery disease. Both cocaine and carbon monoxide can induce myocardial injury through different but converging mechanisms, including increased myocardial oxygen demand, coronary vasoconstriction, endothelial dysfunction, hypoxia, and direct myocardial toxicity. Importantly, myocardial damage may occur even in patients with angiographically normal coronary arteries and may have prognostic implications, particularly in carbon monoxide poisoning. These cases emphasize the importance of considering toxicological etiologies in patients presenting with acute myocardial injury or severe arrhythmias, especially in the absence of conventional cardiovascular risk factors. Careful anamnesis, environmental assessment, and targeted diagnostic evaluation are essential to ensure accurate diagnosis, appropriate management, and effective cardiovascular risk stratification.

Keywords: Carbon monoxide poisoning; Cocaine; Myocardial injury; Toxicology; Ventricular arrhythmias

Cite this paper as: Villa A, Riva V. Acute cardiac injury associated with cocaine use and carbon monoxide exposure: Two case reports. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2026;3(2):210-217. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18111074

Received: 10 June 2025; Revised: 15 October 2025; Accepted: 10 December 2025; Published Online: 31 December 2025

INTRODUCTION

Cocaine is a widely used sympathomimetic drug worldwide, and its production and consumption have increased in recent years, predisposing individuals to the development of multiple pathologies associated with this practice; approximately 5-10% of Emergency Room accesses are assumed to be due to cocaine assumption [1]. In fact, cocaine is the main cause for drug-related visits to the Emergency Room, and most of these are for cardiovascular problems [2]. Also, carbon monoxide intoxications are frequent and can lead to high morbidity and mortality, involving multiple organ systems (among which heart and central nervous system) [3]. We present two case reports to demonstrate the significant clinical relationship between cardiac damage and poisoning or intoxication.

CASE REPORT 1

A 35-year-old male was found unconscious by his father in the tub full of water of the bathroom of his home. The 118 medical doctors, who arrived on site, observed tonic-clonic contractions in the limbs for which he administered midazolam iv; blood pressure was 150/100 mmHg; heart rate 136 beats/minute. During transport in ambulance, oxygen was administered (10 l/min). No pathologies were reported in the past.

On arrival in the Emergency Room the patient showed: coma (GCS = 6); pupils were isochoric, isocyclic of medium size, normally responsive to light; no motor savings were evident in the 4 limbs; reflexes were present, normally evoked. Vital signs were: Blood Pressure: 105/70 mmHg; Heart Rate: 110 beats/minute; Respiratory Rate: 38 breaths/minute; SatO₂: 96% (in oxygen). The electrocardiogram showed a sinus tachycardia with ST depression (>1 mm) in II, III, aVF, V3-V6 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Electrocardiogram on arrival in Emergency Room: sinus tachycardia (115 beats/min), ST depression in DII, DIII, aVF, V3-V6; QT 0.320 sec (QTc 0.394 sec).

Subsequently, the sister arrived and reported the suspicion that the patient had taken cocaine; therefore, the urinary metabolites were searched for (with a qualitative method) and were positive. The research for other substances was negative, blood alcohol level < 10 mg/dl.

Other tests were performed: myoglobin 131 ng/ml (normal value < 70), troponin I 2.08 ng/ml (normal value < 0.14).

About two hours later, upon awakening, the patient, amnesic for the events and asymptomatic (denied chest pain), remembered only going to the bathroom and confirmed the use of inhaled cocaine, but two days before.

A subsequent anamnestic reassessment revealed that there was a gas water heater in the bathroom and the patient already remembered having dizziness and a feeling of lightheadedness while taking a bath. A carboxyhemoglobin dosage was then performed (about 24 hours after the event) which showed a value of 5.9% (the patient was not a smoker).

He was admitted to cardiologic ward to continue observation; the next day an electroencephalogram was performed with a normal result.

An electrocardiogram was repeated with normalization of the repolarization alterations; the troponin showed a constant decrease until normalization; the echocardiogram did not show alterations of the segmental parietal kinesis.

After a few days he was discharged without problems.

CASE REPORT 2

A 45-year-old female presented at the Emergency Room reporting intermittent palpitations for a few hours, which began at work, associated with anxiety and epigastric heaviness; she denied dyspnea. She worked as a beautician, was smoker and reported a hiatal hernia treated with omeprazole.

Vital signs were: Blood Pressure 120/80, Heart Rate 98 beats/minute, rhythmic; SatO₂ 99% (in air).

The electrocardiogram showed: sinus rhythm with ventricular repolarization abnormalities (Figure 2).

Troponin I value was 0.21 ng/ml (normal value < 0.14 ng/ml), while other laboratory tests were normal.

Chest x-ray was normal.

Figure 2. Electrocardiogram on arrival in Emergency Room: sinus rhythm (100 beats/min), in precordial derivations tall, peaked T waves (possible subendocardial ischemia).

About 10 hours after arrival, Troponin I was increased (0.78 ng/ml) and electrocardiographic control was unchanged.

Suddenly, shortly after, a non-sustained ventricular tachycardia appeared on the monitor (Figure 3), which spontaneously regressed and followed by compensatory sinus tachycardia.

Figure 3. Recording from monitoring: non-sustained ventricular tachycardia; subsequent sinus tachycardia.

A rudimentary hookah (Figure 4) used by the patient to inhale cocaine vapor, was found in the drawer of the bedside table, and she admitted to using it.

Figure 4. Rudimental hookah used by patients to inhale cocaine.

The urinary cocaine metabolites were searched for with positive results (with a qualitative method); the Troponin I values showed levels above normal for some days (0.25 - 0.20 ng/ml).

A coronary angiography was performed, and injuries were not shown.

Continuous cardiac monitoring was performed for several days without recording any new episodes of arrhythmia; the patient was then discharged.

DISCUSSION

Neurological and cardiovascular alterations (electrocardiographic changes, signs of myocardial ischemia, and arrhythmias) are described following cocaine use as well as during carbon monoxide intoxication [1-7].

It has been found that approximately 6% of Emergency Room patients treated for chest pain had cocaine-induced myocardial infarction with normal coronary arteries [8, 9].

Cardiac complications in acute cocaine intoxication include sudden death, acute myocarditis, malignant arrhythmias, ischemia and myocardial infarction [10-12].

The most common cocaine-induced electrocardiographic changes are ST-segment elevation, T-wave inversion and QT prolongation; ST-segment depression has been described more rarely. The risk of myocardial infarction is highest within the first hour of cocaine use, but it has been reported that myocardial injury may appear even after several hours due to the action of metabolites, such as benzoylecgonine and ecgonine methyl ester [13,14].

The mechanisms responsible are not fully known, but can include coronary endothelial dysfunction or hypercoagulable state, aortic dissection or aortic wall stiffening.

Cocaine stimulates the release of a potent vasoconstrictor endothelin-1 along with the alpha-adrenergic receptors of the smooth muscle cells of the coronary arteries and inhibits the synthesis of the vasodilator, nitric oxide [15].

Thus, cocaine increases both sympathetic output and catecholamine production; it increases cardiac rate, blood pressure, and cardiac contractility, all of which increases myocardial oxygen demand, and causes vasoconstriction, platelet adherence, thrombus formation, and coronary spasm [15]. Moreover, cocaine reduces sodium transport, and the sodium channel blockade can prolong the QT and QRS intervals and trigger arrhythmias [15].

Also, during carbon monoxide intoxication (even moderate) myocardial lesions may be present, as evidenced by electrocardiographic and cardiac biomarker movement [7, 16].

Carbon monoxide intoxication causes impaired oxygen delivery and utilization at the cellular level, causing hypoxia [7]. As carbon monoxide binds to cardiac myoglobin with even greater affinity than to hemoglobin, myocardial depression and hypotension can further exacerbate tissue hypoxia, leading to myocardial ischemia and damage, even in patients with normal coronary arteries [17-20].

Carbon monoxide may also have direct effects on myocardium; moreover, the role of carbon monoxide in platelet aggregation is controversial, but some studies have indicated increased platelet activation and aggregation in animals [21].

Despite the high frequency of myocardial injury, in-hospital mortality is low (5%); recently, it was reported in a cohort of patients with myocardial injury secondary to acute carbon monoxide intoxication that long-term mortality (7.6 years) was increased compared to the mortality rate of a comparable population for cardiovascular risk factors. Increased troponin was a predictor of long-term mortality [22].

Patients with carbon monoxide intoxication should always be evaluated to exclude myocardial injury and further cardiovascular risk stratification should be considered in all patients with confirmed myocardial injury.

The patient we observed (case 1) manifested a probable seizure and presented a transitory electrocardiographic change due to subendocardial lesion with slight movement of troponin I.

The anamnesis, however difficult, upon the patient's arrival focused on the use of cocaine, but a subsequent in-depth analysis of the exact chronology of events (cocaine intake 2 days before) led to considering this etiology less probable and to consider other toxic causes of the neurological and cardiological alteration, raising the suspicion of carbon monoxide intoxication. Unfortunately, the latency of several hours from the event did not allow us to highlight

high carboxyhemoglobin values, such as to confirm this hypothesis.

Case 2 presented with a potentially malignant arrhythmia. Cocaine is associated with arrhythmia, which may cause moderate to severe symptoms, but there are no specific treatments for cocaine-induced arrhythmia [23]. Lidocaine should be administered with caution, if at all, because it may lower the patient's seizure threshold [23]. Calcium-channel blockers may be useful [23]. Nitroglycerin may be effective at relieving cocaine-induced chest pain by reversing cocaine-related vasoconstriction [24].

The role of beta-blockade in treating the cardiovascular consequences of cocaine use remains controversial [9, 25]. There are no guidelines about the use of beta-blockers in cardiac patients actively using cocaine. The 2014 Guidelines from the American Heart Association and the American College of Cardiology advise against the use of beta-blockers in patients with acute cocaine toxicity because they could potentiate coronary spasm [26]. However, this guidance allows that beta-blockers may be used in patients with non-ST elevation acute coronary syndrome with recent cocaine use [26].

A meta-analysis published in 2019 found no differences between patients with cocaine-associated chest pain treated with beta-blockers and those not treated with beta-blockers in terms of the risk for myocardial infarction [27]. Thus, beta-blockers were not associated with adverse outcomes in cocaine-associated chest pain.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded, therefore, that in young patients, without known cardiovascular risk factors, the etiology of an acute myocardial lesion or of severe arrhythmia should also be sought in the toxicological field.

Author Contributions Conceptualization, study design, resources, data collection, and writing original draft: AV, VR. Study design, methodology, supervision, review, and editing: AV.

Acknowledgments: None.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The Publisher remains neutral regarding jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Additionally, the Publisher is not responsible for the accuracy, completeness, or validity of the content of scientific articles published herein. This statement exempts the Publisher from any responsibility regarding the content of scientific articles, which is solely the responsibility of the authors and peer reviewers.

References

1. Maraj S, Figueredo VM, Morris DL. Cocaine and the heart. *Clin Cardiol.* 2010;33(5):264-269.
2. Havakuk O, Rezkalla SH, Kloner RA. The cardiovascular effects of cocaine. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2017;70(1):101-113.
3. Olson KR. Carbon monoxide poisoning: mechanisms, presentation, and controversies in management. *J Emerg Med.* 1984;1(3):233-243.
4. Barret L, Danel V, Faure J. Carbon monoxide poisoning, a diagnosis frequently overlooked. *J Toxicol Clin Toxicol* 1985;23(4-6):309-313.
5. Prockop LD, Chichkova RI. Carbon monoxide intoxication: an update review. *J Neurol Sci.* 2007;262(1-2):122-130.
6. Talarico GP, Crosta ML, Giannico MB, Summari F, Calò L, Patrizi R. Cocaine and coronary artery diseases: a systematic review of the literature. *J Cardiovasc Med (Hagerstown).* 2017;18(5):291-294.
7. Jankowska D, Palabindala V, Salim SA. Non-ST elevation myocardial infarction secondary to carbon monoxide intoxication. *J Community Hosp Intern Med Perspect.* 2017;7(2):130-133.
8. Whyte G, Godfrey R, O'Hanlon R, Wilson M, Buckley J, Sharma S. Acute myocardial infarction in the presence of normal coronaries and the absence of risk factors in a young, lifelong regular exerciser. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2009; 2009:bcr07.2008.0384.

9. Pergolizzi JV Jr, Magnusson P, LeQuang JA, Breve F, Varrassi G. Cocaine and cardiotoxicity: a literature review. *Cureus*. 2021;13(4):e14594.
10. Nanji AA, Filipenko JD. Asystole and ventricular fibrillation with cocaine intoxication. *Chest*. 1984;85(1):132-133.
11. Pasternack PF, Colvin SB, Baumann FG. Cocaine-induced angina pectoris and acute myocardial infarction in patients younger than 40 years. *Am J Cardiol*. 1985;55(6):847.
12. Peng SK, French WJ, Pelikan PC. Direct cocaine cardiotoxicity demonstrated by endomyocardial biopsy. *Arch Pathol Lab Med*. 1989;113(8):842-845.
13. Lange RA, Hillis LD. Cardiovascular complications of cocaine use. *N Engl J Med*. 2001;345(5):351-358.
14. McCord J, Jneid JE, Hollander JA, de Lemos JA, Cercek B, Hsue P, et al. Management of cocaine-associated chest pain and myocardial infarction: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association Acute Cardiac Care Committee of the Council on Clinical Cardiology. *Circulation*. 2008;117(14):1897-1907.
15. Schwartz BG, Rezkalla S, Kloner RA. Cardiovascular effects of cocaine. *Circulation*. 2010;122(24):2558-2569.
16. Satran D, Henry CR, Adkinson C, Nicholson CI, Bracha Y, Henry TD. Cardiovascular manifestations of moderate to severe carbon monoxide poisoning. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2005;45(9):1513-1516.
17. Marius-Nunez AL. Myocardial infarction with normal coronary arteries after acute exposure to carbon monoxide. *Chest*. 1990;97(2):491-494.
18. Lee D, Hsu TL, Chen CH, Wang SP, Chang MS. Myocardial infarction with normal coronary artery after carbon monoxide exposure: a case report. *Zhonghua Yi Xue Za Zhi (Taipei)*. 1996;57(5):355-359.
19. Raub JA, Mathieu-Nolf M, Hampson NB, Thom SR. Carbon monoxide poisoning--a public health perspective. *Toxicology*. 2000;145(1):1-14.
20. Szponar J, KoloSzponar J, Kołodziej M, Majewska M, Zaleski K, Lewandowska-Stanek H. Myocardial injury in the course of carbon monoxide poisoning. *Przegl Lek*. 2012;69(8):528-534.
21. Gering SA, Folts JD. Exacerbation of acute platelet thrombus formation in stenosed dog coronary arteries with smoke from a non-tobacco-burning cigarette. *J Lab Clin Med*. 1990;116(5):728-736.
22. Henry CR, Satran D, Lindgren B, Adkinson C, Nicholson CI, Henry TD. Myocardial injury and long-term mortality following moderate to severe carbon monoxide poisoning. *JAMA*. 2006;295(4):398-402.
23. Kuczkowski KM. More on the idiosyncratic effects of cocaine on the human heart. *Emerg Med J*. 2007;24(2):147.
24. Baumann BM, Perrone J, Hornig SE, Shofer FS, Hollander JE. Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of diazepam, nitroglycerin, or both for treatment of patients with potential cocaine-associated acute coronary syndromes. *Acad Emerg Med*. 2000;7(8):878-885.
25. Gatto L, Frati G, Biondi-Zoccai G, Versaci F. Cocaine and acute coronary syndromes: novel management insights for this clinical conundrum. *Int J Cardiol*. 2018;260:16-17.
26. Amsterdam EA, Wenger NK, Brindis RG, Casey DE Jr, Ganiats TG, Holmes DR Jr, et al. 2014 AHA/ACC Guideline for the management of patients with Non-ST-Elevation acute coronary syndromes: a report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Practice Guidelines. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2014;64(24):e139-e228.
27. Lo KB, Virk HUH, Lakhter V, Ram P, Gongora C, Pressman G, et al. Clinical outcomes after treatment of cocaine-induced chest pain with beta-blockers: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Med*. 2019;132(4):505-509.

